

A PREVALENCE OF PARAMPHISTOMES IN COASTAL AREA OF ANDHRA PRADESH

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Paramphistome infections in ruminants cause considerable economical losses to farmers. Santra *et al* (1996) estimated the economical losses incidental to various livestock diseases; of those diarrhoea due to various etiological factors account for the maximum (59.42%) losses. Among the helminthic parasites of ruminants, paramphistomes (rumen flukes) are the most common and pathogenic (Pat *et al.*, 2001). The incidence of paramphistomosis has been reported in different states of India. (Varma *et al.*, 1989 and Manna *et al.* 1994). Several species of amphistomes have been reported in domesticated animals in India. (Prasad *et al.*, 1999). The present study has been undertaken to elucidate the prevalence of paramphistome infection of buffaloes in coastal area of Krishna district of Andhra Pradesh highlighting seasonal incidence.

Materials and Methods

All those clinical cases which were brought to the Veterinary Polyclinic. Gudiwada with the history of anorexia, decreased milk yield, foetid-diarrhoea, repeat breeding and oedema of intermandibular space, brisket were selected for the study. Faecal samples were collected either per rectum or from

freshly voided dung. The dung samples were examined by direct smear method, sedimentation technique qualitatively and identification was done based on the morphological characters of amphistome ova as described by Soulsby (1986). A total of 2,085 faecal samples were examined. Besides this routine faecal examination, the Municipal Kabela (Municipal Slaughter House) was visited several times for post-mortem examination and for certification of meat.

Results and Discussion

Out of 2,085 samples examined, 918 were found positive for parasitic ova in which 430 samples (prevalence 20.14%) were positive for amphistome eggs. The high prevalence rate of 20.14% showed that amphistomosis alone accounted for nearly 50% of the total parasitic diseases diagnosed. Highest incidence of amphistomosis (25.72%) was recorded during monsoon and post monsoon season (July to October) followed by summer (19.09%) season (March to June) and least during winter (16.05%) season (November to February). The reasons could be attributed to increased intermediate host, snail population (*Indoplanorbis exustus*, *Gyraulus convexiusculus* and *Lymnaea*

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luteola) during rainy season. Further, the metacercariae, which get concentrated during summer in marshy stagnant water suddenly, spreads like an outbreak with the showers of monsoon. The wallowing habit of buffaloes is also partly responsible for the high incidence. Moreover, the study area itself is a low-lying and highly irrigated area, which also aggravates the condition. These findings corroborated the earlier findings of Dhoot *et al.* (2002) and Sahoo *et al.* (2003) who reported higher incidence of parasitic infection during rainy season.

Of 18 postmortem cases attended, 12 were found positive and of 90 animals slaughtered for meat, 36 were found positive for amphistomosis. Necropsy findings were subcutaneous oedema, accumulation of fluids in the body cavities, gelatinous fat depots in some cases, thickened upper part of the duodenal mucosa covered with blood stained mucus (severe enteritis). In most of the cases, obstruction of bile duct by the *Gigantocotyle explanatum* was witnessed and butchers reported the same.

Paramphistomosis causes major production loss often without clinical manifestation also. Adult flukes are less pathogenic as compared to immature flukes because of their plug feeding on the duodenal mucosa. Immature flukes cause high mortality and morbidity in ruminants (Blood, 1994). The paramphistome species was predominant when compared to other helminthic infections during all seasons. These findings are in agreement with the

findings of Sahoo *et al.* (*loc.cit.*) Bhattacharyya *et al.* (2005), and Sanyal (1989).

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